

COMPOSITES IN SPORTING GOODS APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The composite ice hockey stick industry is a highly dynamic and competitive marketplace where the materials and technologies used are quite similar to those applied in aerospace and Formula One race cars. Furthermore, loading conditions are highly complex and involve very high applied strains, while development timelines are very tight. Therefore, FEA models are used to conceptualize and evaluate designs.

The first challenge to developing an effective FEA model is to acquire an accurate set of boundary conditions. This is particularly complex given the loads applied by a player in a series of simultaneous, semi-independent movements: pre-bending the stick, making puck contact, and finally directing the puck towards the target. Instrumenting sticks with strain-gauges, optical fibres, 3-D motion tracking devices or other can change the inertia and bending properties of the stick. Therefore, we see the need for research that could support development of new measuring methods and technologies.

The second challenge is the limited database of relevant material properties at our disposal. When producing hollow tubes and other intricate shapes, it is not uncommon to experience lower and/or non-uniform pressure and temperature during the manufacturing process. These can have significant effects on the material properties and the precision of our existing FEA models. Likewise, information on the effects of curing and post-curing conditions are often unavailable. To that regard, more research is warranted for material properties for higher strain rates, non-ambient temperatures and hybrid structures.

The third challenge is that the vast amount of existing impact data is specific to high-mass, single-impact applications where the structure absorbs energy via failure. In our particular application, we are looking to achieve a multi-impact structure that can withstand loads without compromising structural integrity.

Structural failure in our application is often progressive and due to a combination of impacts and high strains. Unfortunately, the simulation of progressive failure in a FEA model is highly complex and requires substantial time and resources to validate and perform. Therefore, we would like to see more research on modeling progressive failure, leading to the development of more effective methods to simulate the change in mechanical properties.

The final, and perhaps most complex, challenge is predicting performance for a given structure. Understanding that the player could adjust his mechanics in consequence of the stick's properties, this is a somewhat circular, highly iterative and interactive model. Once again, having the technologies to record multiple precise measurements at a high frequency would significantly impact our ability to advance our products at a steeper development rate.

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INTRODUCTION

The sporting goods industry is a dynamic and highly competitive marketplace where optimized performance and advanced technology are not only expected, but demanded. Materials, technologies, and research methods from the aerospace industry have made their way into sporting goods applications, which has consequently led to great advances in performance and, in some cases, a change in the way sports are even played.

Among these new technologies, the use of composite materials, carbon fibre in particular, has had a significant impact on the design of ice hockey sticks. Likewise for aerospace applications, the key advantages to carbon fibre are lighter weight structures, higher energy return and greater freedom of design. Even with such technological advances, however, ice hockey stick engineers must continually drive and improve upon product performance and strength in order to stay ahead of the competition.

While composite materials have allowed us to enhance overall performance, they present many challenges from a manufacturing and design standpoint. Again, similar to aerospace, high velocity impacts and resistance to fatigue from high strains represent two of the biggest challenges faced by engineers. Furthermore, these two dynamics are often coupled in a single region of the structure, which subsequently lead to progressive failure from a combination of the two phenomena.

Improving player performance is highly complex: the hockey player applies multiple, non-linear dynamic forces. As such, timing is critical; and more often than not, athletes will adjust their movement and forces in consequence of a given design. Therefore, the design process is often highly iterative and interactive and, in some cases, player education is required to achieve the optimum combination of product performance and playing technique.

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is intrinsic to the design process as it allows us to 1) reduce the number of iterations produced, 2) better understand the behaviour of each individual ply inside the structure, and 3) save development time and cost. At the same time, a model is only as effective as the accuracy of its input values. As such, we are looking to develop new measuring methods and technologies to establish precise boundary conditions in our models. At the same time, we require a broader database of mechanical properties of materials for evaluation and modelling purposes. Finally, we are looking to develop better, more user-friendly tools to predict progressive failure in composite materials and performance.

The objective of this paper is thus to highlight our needs with regards to research and development support, with the aim to reduce weight, increase overall strength and ultimately enhance the performance of our stick designs.

Requirement #1 - Develop an effective FEA Model

Development timelines in the sporting goods industry are extremely short. Furthermore, product requirements can change quickly as players adapt their technique to new coaching, training and game play methods. Constant innovation is critical to staying ahead of the competition; as such, simulation using Finite Element Analysis has become an intrinsic part of the development process for cost and time savings.

Modelling an ice hockey stick is not an easy task. The monolithic structure is formed from a long, hollow shaft integrated with a sandwich structure blade. Some blades can employ multiple cores made of different materials. In turn, the structure can be comprised of unidirectional pre-preg plies, spread-tow fabrics, heavy fabrics, dry materials, aerospace foams and toughened resins. The structure must withstand a combination of multiple impacts and very high strains, while at the same time provide a dynamic and precise response when loaded by the player.

All of the aforementioned materials and load cases require individual as well as combined studies in order to build effective models.

One of the challenges that we are facing is to develop an FEA model with an accurate set of boundary conditions and an optimal meshing method. Current models employ different methods; static, modal and explicit dynamic models are the most popular. Composite layers are either modelled as shells for mechanical purposes or modelled as solid or thick shell elements for impact models. Static models are useful to provide a global view of stick behaviour, also known as the “flex profile”.

A hockey stick’s flex profile is not strictly linear: “Kick points”, which are isolated regions of lower stiffness, are designed into the structure to allow for a specific behaviour during shooting. In simple form, a higher kick point will generate a longer pendulum and higher energy storage. In turn, a lower kick point will have a shorter pendulum and thus a quicker response. The player’s technique and playing style will determine the way he or she prefers the stick to bend. During a shot, the player bends the shaft and stores energy in the carbon fibre, similar to a shooting bow or a catapult. When the shaft recoils, the energy is used to accelerate the puck.

Figure 1 – Stick Flex Profiles: the redder the stick, the softer it is

Flex profiles are measured by performing a series of cantilever bend tests along the length of the stick. This test methodology can be reproduced in FEA models, thus allowing us to design and validate a flex profile without physically building a sample. From there, we measure how this flex profile influences the strain rate and strain distribution during shooting movement.

Developmentally, the ability to measure multiple, instantaneous strains on a stick would be extremely advantageous. The use of strain gauges is feasible, however, it involves permanently mounting strain gauges on a stick, which requires a great deal of wiring that ultimately add- significant

inertia to the stick and can potentially interfere with the shooting mechanics. As such, it is a complicated endeavour. Optical fibers are an excellent option for taking multiple strain readings. However, these too can change the inertia and modulus of the structure. An excellent step forward would be to develop a method for measuring strains in real-time, without modifying stick mechanics (weight, centre of gravity, surface shape, etc.).

The use of FEA models shows great potential in this regard, however, sample correlation is required for model validation. Moreover, the creation of such FEA models would require boundary conditions data such as hand position, forces and pressures applied at different places along the stick, to name but a few.

Creating a realistic model of this kind would significantly advance product development. This would require a comprehensive biomechanical study combined with in-depth mechanical analysis.

Figure 2 - Overlay of High Speed Video and FEA Model

Requirement #2 – Develop effective methods to simulate the change in mechanical properties as a result of progressive failure modelling

Another challenge related to FEA modelling is establishing the correct mechanical properties for the material in the structure. While a significant amount of data is not required to develop a static model, it is, however, required to accurately predict failure modes.

A material's mechanical properties are heavily influenced by the moulding process and/or curing cycles used. It is common for material suppliers to provide mechanical properties based on testing of thin, homogeneous plaques produced on a small linear press. However, the properties measured from plaques produced under near-perfect conditions can be significantly different to the properties achieved with the same materials in a hollow structure and/or complex shape where it is very difficult to generate the same pressure and uniform temperature. As a result, FEA models built from published material properties may not accurately predict the mechanical behaviour of composite structures.

With access to a lab that could produce multiple samples in different profiles using a variety of curing cycles, pressures, resin contents, resin flows, testing temperatures, and strain-rates, material properties that more closely resemble reality could be attainable. In fact, the creation of such a database could contribute to the reduction of real sample trials, ultimately resulting in quicker development timelines and reduced costs.

By definition, composite materials are made of a mix of different materials. As such, mechanical properties for many combinations of fibre and resin already exist. However, there is little information available for hybrid fabrics and structures (composed of multiple fibres), despite their obvious benefits in today's manufacturing landscape. Similarly, the use of sandwich structures is now seen in a many different applications. Given that the interface between core and skin can have a huge influence on how it will behave, the characterization of such structures would be warranted to enhance FEA model accuracy and feasibility. As such, further hybridization of products involves integrating different materials (carbon fibres, thermoset resins, thermoplastic polymers, metal or ceramic inserts) with different processes (autoclave, resin transfer moulding, injection, over-moulding, press-fitting, ultrasonic welding) on a single part. Here, the industry would benefit significantly from having the ability to simulate the hybrid structures inclusive of the interface dynamics.

For example, if a carbon fibre plaque is over-moulded with a polyethylene based thermoplastic, a standard test will provide the average elasticity modulus, density and strength. But what about the moment where the nylon delaminates from the carbon fibre plaque? If it's only over-moulded (a pure chemical bond), this moment could be considered as the ultimate strength of the hybrid material. In other cases, materials are fused by a combination of chemical and mechanical bonding. In those cases, the ultimate strength is determined quite differently. The behaviour of these hybrid materials are highly non-linear and depend on material history. New testing standards are now required. These standards could be established by internal labs, external labs, universities, or even bigger institutions like ASTM tests.

Requirement # 3 – Create a shared material properties database

The creation of a shared database could drive innovation and provide engineers and developers with an easier and more convenient way to compare and exchange solutions. Ideally, this database would also include some FEA models of plaques with validated properties for reference purposes.

With regards to hockey sticks, FEA composite failure prediction is a state-of-the-art model. As outlined in the aforementioned paragraphs, such modelling requires a significant amount of material data. For this reason, failure models are relatively new to industrial applications, whereas they have been utilized for a few years in research and development. Once more, the bulk of information available on failure models is based on single impact / ballistic type failure, and relatively little information exist on progressive / multi-impact failure.

The amount of data collected on coupons and other simple geometries for research purposes is greater than the data available from finished products. With such rapid timelines, manufacturers simply do not have time to make coupons to accumulate data. This is not to say that no lab testing is done in the industry; the testing performed, however, is usually product-oriented, measuring performance and durability in the product environment.

Requirement #4 – Develop technology to take multiple precise measurements at a high frequency

Composite failure prediction always depends on the load case, which is why new measurement methods must be developed. Once created, the next step would be to apply current algorithms of explicit dynamics. As it stands, the only way to simulate composite failure using explicit dynamics models is to first create thin solid elements or thick shell elements and then run the lengthy and time-consuming calculation.

At a certain point during the stick modelling process, it is important to estimate the impact of small geometrical modifications. The latter imply having a finer meshing, which, in the explicit dynamic method, defines the length of time each step takes in the calculation: the finer the meshing, the longer the calculation.

Figure 3 - Explicit Stick Failure Model

In hockey sticks, failure rarely occurs during a single shot. Breakage is most often due to a combination of the stick's impact and strain history. These models can be classified as low mass-high velocity impacts + large displacements generating high strains. Models of this kind are scarce. Furthermore, developing them in parallel with development timelines is challenging. By the time a model is validated, many product iterations will have been evaluated and the design evolved. Moreover, it is often difficult to justify the time spent to develop a model of this complexity when improvements can be made through trial and error using fewer resources given today's technology. This is why industrial players need research partners who can develop such models and provide a simplified process to model a product's impact history (combination of slashes, puck impacts and bending fatigue).

We have discussed at great length modeling structures to predict failure and improve strength. However, we have not discussed the opportunity to use simulation models for performance measurement and optimization. This is highly complex as "performance" can be associated with several mechanical measurements, such as loading speed, recoil speed and player's biomechanics. Of course, as noted earlier, these dynamics will be influenced by the player's input and overall technique. Other characteristics associated with performance and "feel" such as the coefficient of restitution (how fast the puck leaves the surface) and the dampening coefficient (how much or how little we can feel the impact). In all cases, the model is complex because we are ultimately looking for a prediction or measurement of how the entire structure behaves, and not just a particular material.

Ultimately, a good performing product will consist of an optimized balance of these properties.

Therefore, an effective FEA model for performance optimization would require the ability to evaluate each of these dynamic properties of a hybrid structure under the precise loading conditions applied by a player.

Figure 4 – Stick Handling by Patrick Kane

In Figure 4, the player isn't bending the stick (or using any mechanical property of the stick), he is simply "feeling" the puck through the stick in order to successfully manoeuvre it through the maze of pucks without touching any of them.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the sporting goods industry is a dynamic and highly competitive marketplace where optimized performance and advanced technology must be achieved along rapid development timelines. The use of composite materials has had a significant impact to product performance, providing lighter weight structures, higher energy return and greater freedom of design. At the same time, they present many challenges from a design and manufacturing standpoint. Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is intrinsic to the design process as it allows us to reduce the number of iterations, better understand material behaviour, and save development time and costs. At the same time, a model is only as effective as the accuracy of its input values. Establishing accurate boundary conditions is highly complex based on player mechanics. As such, we are looking to develop new measuring methods and technologies to establish precise boundary conditions in our models. At the same time, we require a broader database of mechanical properties of materials for evaluation and modelling purposes. Finally, we are looking to develop better, more user-friendly tools to predict progressive failure in composite materials and performance. The objective of this paper is thus to highlight our needs with regards to research and development support, with the aim to reduce weight, increase overall strength and ultimately enhance product performance.